

Generalising Stable Sets of Cooperative Games Using Abstract Argumentation

M1107-CMS05 RESEARCH PROJECT

TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF DRESDEN

BY

PARAMITA CHOUDHURY

SUPERVISED BY

DR. HABIL. HANNES STRASS

DECEMBER 5, 2024

Abstract. This is a compilation of correspondences of various concepts from cooperative game theory and abstract argumentation theory. We have verified abstract frameworks semantics as potential solution concepts for cooperative games. The semantics, considered, are stable, preferred, complete, and grounded semantics. These solution concepts have been analyzed in terms of existence, uniqueness, and interrelationships with the core using the abstract AF semantics.

1 Introduction

We encounter arguments and games nearly every day in different aspects of our lives. In fact, without engaging in arguments, humanity might not have been able to broaden its knowledge or even survive, as the absence of argumentation would have hindered identification of many problems. On the other hand, games also have played a role in developing strategies to solve problems and achieve goals. While certain scenarios demand individual success, others reveal that an individual's well-being depends on the collective's prosperity. The later is explored in cooperative game theory where various models try to maximize not only individual's but also a coalition's profit. Argumentation and cooperative game theory both are extensively used in logic, computer science and artificial intelligence. We shall explore and verify relation between argumentation and cooperative game theory in the rest of the report.

Let's look at one argumentation example where Alex and Bill, two friends, are debating over the necessity of urbanization.

Example 1 (Argumentation). Consider the following example:

- Alex: Urban growth demands city expansion into forests to ensure housing, a vital factor for better quality of life.
- Bill: Urbanization fosters inequality as rural migrants often struggle to integrate into city life. Additionally, factors such as overcrowding contribute to worsening city living conditions.
- Alex: Urbanization is essential for economic growth, which is crucial for the overall development of civilization.
- Bill: Deforestation to expand cities worsens climate change and depletes ecosystems. One of the major drivers of deforestation is urbanization.

If this were a conversation between the leaders of two countries, instead of two friends, the dynamics would change. Let's say country-A has vast forest cover but a weak economy, while country-B has a strong economy and limited natural resources

such as land. Both countries are facing population growth. In this case, the conversation would shift to strategic negotiations. For country-A, the easiest path to economic growth and accommodation for people might be natural resource extraction one form of which is deforestation. Meanwhile, country-B would likely address its housing shortage by building vertical cities, creating a concrete jungle due to its scarcity of natural resources. However, a smarter solution would be for both countries to form a coalition based on how to share resources and preserve nature so that both parties can benefit more. Ultimately, the outcome of the negotiation would depend on which country holds the stronger bargaining position.

Argumentation theory is the branch of artificial intelligence (AI) that is concerned with the rational and transparent resolution of disagreements between arguments [3]. Abstract Argumentation theory, as articulated in Phan Minh Dung's seminal work [7] represents argumentation theory in an abstract manner as it considers the arguments by stripping off all the features such as characteristics, origin, etc. An argument cannot be *accepted* if the knowledge-base contains conflicting arguments. Dung named these conflicts as *attack*. His work focused on finding the *acceptable set of arguments* in a given a knowledge base following specific set of rules.

Cooperative game theory is the study of mathematical models where rational agents form coalitions to get more profit than they could have individually. Unlike non-cooperative game theory the players here enter into binding contract, work jointly and increase their overall gain. In non-cooperative games, the players are selfish but not adversarial. In contract, in cooperative games, the players are not exactly altruistic. They only care to join a coalition to maximize their own profit.

Human beings often engage in arguments and provide justifications for their actions. A fact is considered established when no further counterarguments remain. This process is a common framework for addressing problems in social and economical structures. Similarly, individuals analyze situations and form coalitions to collaboratively solve problems while pursuing their personal goals. Dung used cooperative game theory to demonstrate the correctness of *abstract argumentation theory* and the *acceptability semantics* as one of the relevant and convincing examples [7, Section 3] by establishing connection between solution concepts of cooperative game theory and acceptability semantics of abstract AF. Dung's work was limited to some specific AF semantics. Young et al. extended the correspondence between Dung's four argumentation semantics and the various solution concepts [16]. The following sections of this report will provide an overview of Abstract Argumentation theory and Cooperative Game Theory, explore the connection between them as demonstrated by Dung and Young et al., and conclude with suggestions for future work.

2 Background

2.1 Abstract Argumentation Theory

We shall first describe an overview of how an argument gets *accepted* in an AF. The following steps have been elaborated in figure 1. First, the arguments are derived from a foundational knowledge base. In figure 1, the arguments are A_1, A_2 and A_3 . Next, the presence of counterarguments for each argument is examined, allowing conflicts to be identified. This process forms the argumentation framework, visualized as a directed graph where the arguments are represented as nodes and the conflicts between them are represented as arrows. After this stage, details about conflicts and the internal structure of arguments are abstracted away and we get an abstract framework S containing only the arguments and conflict. Using this framework, decisions are made about which arguments to accept in order to reach a conclusion. Now, we shall review the notion of Argumentation Theory as proposed by Dung.

Definition 1 (Argumentation framework [7]). *An argumentation framework is a pair $F = (\text{Arg}, \text{attacks})$ where*

- Arg is a set of arguments
- $\text{attacks} \subseteq \text{Arg} \times \text{Arg}$ is a binary relation on Arg .

For $a, b \in \text{Arg}$, $\text{attacks}(a, b)$ means argument a represents an attack to argument b . Effectively, it means argument a disagrees with argument b .

Definition 2 (Conflict-free). *Let $F = (\text{Arg}, \text{attacks})$ be an AF. A set $S \subseteq \text{Arg}$ is conflict-free in F , iff there is no $(a, b) \in S$ such that $(a, b) \in \text{attacks}$.*

A set S of arguments is said to be conflict-free iff there are no two arguments a, b in S such that a attacks b or b attacks a . For $S \subseteq \text{Arg}$, $S^+ = \{b \in \text{Arg} \mid \exists a \in S \text{ and } \text{attacks}(a, b)\}$ represents set of arguments attacked by S . $S \cup S^+$ is called *range* of S . Similar to S^+ , there will be $S^- = \{b \in \text{Arg} \mid \exists a \in S \text{ and } \text{attacks}(b, a)\}$. We say that an argument a attacks a set of arguments S iff it attacks at least one argument in S . We say that a set of arguments S attacks an argument a iff at least one argument in S attacks a . We say that a set of arguments S_1 attacks a set of arguments S_2 iff at least one argument in S_1 attacks at least one argument in S_2 [4].

Definition 3 (Defence). *Let $F = (\text{Arg}, \text{attacks})$ be an AF. $S \subseteq \text{Arg}$ defends an argument a iff $a^- \subseteq S^+$.*

Fig. 1. Overall process

This means every attacker of argument a is being attacked by some argument from set of arguments S . The notion of *defence* has been mentioned as part of characteristic function in definition 16 of [7].

Definition 4 (Admissible). *A set S is admissible iff it is both conflict-free and admissble.*

The empty set is admissible for any argumentation framework.

Fig. 2. A simple AF

Example 2. In figure 2, we have a simple argumentation framework where argument a_1 attacks a_2 and a_2 attacks a_3 . Following the above definitions, we can see $\text{Arg} = \{a_1, a_2, a_3\}$ and $\text{attacks} = \{(a_1, a_2), (a_2, a_3)\}$. *Conflict-free* and *admissible* set of arguments, respectively, are $Cf_{\text{Arg}} = \{\{a_1\}, \{a_2\}, \{a_3\}, \{a_1, a_3\}, \emptyset\}$ and $\text{Adm}_{\text{Arg}} = \{\{a_1\}, \{a_1, a_3\}, \emptyset\}$. The reason for conflict-freeness is clear. As for admissibility, a_1 is included trivially as there is no attack. In the second set, a_3 is included as the attacker of a_3 is being attacked by a_1 effectively defending it. But a_3 cannot defend itself alone. If there were an attack relation from a_3 to a_2 , we could have included $\{a_3\}$ as a self defending argument.

2.2 Cooperative Game Theory

Dung demonstrated "correctness" of theory of abstract AF using cooperative game theory as an example. This demonstration established the correspondence between some of the semantics of abstract AF and cooperative game theory.

Cooperative game theory is the branch of game theory that studies "how non-rationally rational agents may cooperate in order to possibly earn more payoff than they would do as individuals" [16]. In simpler words, it is a decision-making tool for rational agents that first helps them clarify *what* they want to achieve, then guides them on *how* best to achieve it [6]. Answer to the former, i.e. "*what* they want to achieve", is *maximize their payoff*. In order to do so, in cooperative game, the players or the rational agents create coalition. The overall payoff of the coalition is

distributed among the members of the coalition. This is the transferable utility of the coalition. This will be worth mentioning that a player will join a coalition only if it increases the individual's payoff.

We now shall now look into some of the concepts and formal definitions of cooperative game theory.

Definition 5 (Cooperative Game). *A cooperative game with transferable utility is a pair $G = (P, v)$ where*

- $P = \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ is the set of players.
- $v : 2^P \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ is the characteristic function (sometimes also referred to as the coalitional function), which for each subset (or coalition) $C \subseteq P$ of players indicates the utility (or gain) $v(C)$ that these players attain by working together. Here $\mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ denotes the set of nonnegative real numbers [15].

The characteristic function v of such a game $G = (P, v)$ has the following properties [16]:

1. Normalization: $v(\emptyset) = 0$.
2. Monotonicity: $v(C) \leq v(D)$ for all coalitions C and D with $C \subseteq D$.
3. Super-additivity: For all $C, D \subseteq P$, if C, D are disjoint then $v(C \cup D) \geq v(C) + v(D)$.
4. Constant-sum: v is constant-sum iff $(\forall C \subseteq N)v(C) + v(N - C) = v(N)$.
5. Inessential: v is inessential iff $\sum_{k=1}^n v(k) = v(P)$.

Among the properties mentioned above, we will use the first three to illustrate further new concepts.

Definition 6 (Coalition structure). *Let $G = (P, v)$ be a cooperative game (with transferable utility). A coalition structure for G is a partition $\mathcal{C} = \{C_1, \dots, C_n\}$ of P , that is,*

- $C_1, \dots, C_n \subseteq P$.
- $C_1 \cup \dots \cup C_n = P$.
- $C_i \cap C_j = \emptyset$ for all $1 \leq i \neq j \leq n$.

In a cooperative game with n -players, there are 2^n coalitions. The coalition structure $\mathcal{C} = \{P\}$ is called the grand coalition.

The term "*transferable utility*" indicates that players in a coalition can exchange money with one another, allowing them to divide the coalition's overall *payoff* in any way they prefer. There are also cooperative games with nontransferable utility but in this report, we shall focus only on cooperative games with transferable utility. We shall examine the notions of payoff distribution within a coalition structure in the next section.

Definition 7 (Outcome). *An outcome of a cooperative game $G = (P, v)$ with transferable utility is given by a pair $(\mathcal{C}, \mathbf{x})$, where \mathcal{C} is a coalition structure and $\mathbf{x} = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) \in \mathbb{R}_n$ is a payoff vector such that $x_i \geq 0$ for each $i \in P$ and $\sum_{i \in C} x_i = v(C)$ for each coalition $C \in \mathcal{C}$.*

In a superadditive game, any two coalitions can merge without incurring any loss. The worst-case scenario for such a game arises when the value of the newly merged coalition is simply the sum of the two original coalitions, with no additional gain from the synergy of merging. This motivates the rational agents to form grand coalition in such game. The payoff of grand coalition is denoted as $v(P)$.

Let us now look into an example which will illustrate the above definitions.

Table 1. 3-player cooperative game

Coalition member	Avg Investment	Selling price	Sellers' gain	Buyer's gain
$C_5 = S_1, B$	8	13	5	12
$C_6 = S_2, B$	8	11	3	14
$C_7 = S_1, S_2, B$	8	18	10	7
$C_7 = S_1, S_2, B$	8	17	9	8

Example 3 (Cooperative Game Theory). Let's assume in a market there are few sellers offering similar products. A buyer wants to buy one of those similar products at lowest possible price. Sellers want to maximize their profit. We shall look into this scenario in a cooperative game theoretic construct. We shall consider two sellers and the buyer from this market. The three players of this game are, $P = \{S_1, S_2, B\}$. The purpose of this game is to sell the product. Let's assume market value of the product from other sellers is at least 25 euro. Hence, we calculate buyer's gain by subtracting selling price from 25 euro. We get total gain by summing up sellers' and buyer's gain.

Non-empty coalitions are, $C_1 = \{S_1\}$, $C_2 = \{S_2\}$, $C_3 = \{B\}$, $C_4 = \{S_1, S_2\}$, $C_5 = \{S_1, B\}$, $C_6 = \{S_2, B\}$ and $C_7 = \{S_1, S_2, B\}$. Clearly, coalitions C_1, C_2, C_3 and C_4 are not useful as no product can be sold in these coalitions. So, $v(C_1) = v(C_2) = v(C_3) = v(C_4) = 0$ and $v(C_5) = v(C_6) = v(C_7) = 17$. Following table 1, we can

see the two seller make higher profit when they form an alliance(refer last two rows elaborating two different payoff for grand coalition). In this case, a possible *payoff vector* for coalition structure $\mathcal{C}_7 = \{\{S_1, S_2, B\}\}$ can be $\mathbf{x}_1 = (7, 3, 7)$ where the first and second seller divide the profit as 7 and 3 euro between them. The buyer gets to save 7 euro. Thus we get a possible *outcome*, $(\mathcal{C}_7, \mathbf{x}_1)$. There can be many more outcomes depending on how the profit is distributed, such as $\mathbf{x}_2 = (6, 3, 7)$.

It is easy to see that the game follows *normalization*. The characteristics function is *monotonic*. If we consider coalitions C_1, C_3, C_5 and C_7 it is clear that their gain is following the inequalities in the order of ascending inclusion chain. For $C_1, C_3 \subseteq C_5 \subseteq C_7$, we have $v(C_1), v(C_3) \leq v(C_5) \leq v(C_7)$. When the possible disjoint sets of coalitions are considered, it becomes evident that the game is *superadditive* also. For example, $v(C_7) \geq v(C_3) \cup v(C_4)$.

3 From Cooperative Game Theory to Abstract Argumentation

3.1 Acceptability semantics

The framework illustrated in example 2 prompts several questions:

- Which set of arguments will be accepted?
- How can we determine the process of acceptance?
- Will there be a single solution, multiple solutions, or no solution at all?

Thus we arrive at the *acceptability semantics* for an argumentation framework $F = (\text{Arg}, \text{attacks})$ and set $S \subseteq \text{Arg}$. Two main approaches have been described by Baroni et al.[12] to the definition of argumentation semantics: *labelling*-based approach and *extension*-based approach. They have mentioned that "the extension-based approach can be regarded as a special case of the general labelling-based approach". Here, we shall concentrate only on *extension*-based approach following Dung's notion.

An extension is sets of arguments which can survive the conflict together and thus represents collectively a reasonable position a rational agent might take. Specific extension-based argumentation semantics defines a method for selecting *reasonable* sets of arguments from all possible options, *based on criteria established in its definition*.

We shall now look into some of the formal counterparts and examples of the notions described above. We will also examine them in terms of their existence and uniqueness. *Existence* is defined as the property that ensures the semantics generate at least one result for every argumentation framework. *Uniqueness*, on the other hand, implies whether the semantics produce exactly one result for every argumentation framework.

Definition 8 (Acceptability Semantics). Let $F = (\text{Arg}, \text{attacks})$ be an AF. A set $S \subseteq \text{Arg}$ is called -

- **Naive:** iff it is subset maximal conflict free set.
- **Complete:** iff each admissible $a \in \text{Arg}$ defended by S is contained in S .
- **Grounded:** iff it is the minimal (w.r.t set-inclusion) complete extension.
- **Preferred:** iff it is subset-maximally admissible set.
- **Stable:** iff for each conflict-free $a \in \text{Arg} \setminus S$, there exists $b \in S$ such that $(b, a) \in \text{attacks}$.
- **Semi-Stable:** iff it is range maximal admissible set.
- **Stage:** iff it is range maximal conflict free set.
- **Ideal:** iff S is admissible and it is contained in every preferred set of arguments [8].
- **Eager:** iff S is the greatest (w.r.t. set-inclusion) admissible set that is a subset of each semi-stable extension [4].

Fig. 3. An argumentation framework with all extensions

We will now look into two examples to understand how the semantics are derived.

Example 4 (Argumentation framework). (Continuation of Example 1). We shall rewrite the statements as below:

a_4 : "Urban growth demands city expansion into forests to ensure housing, a vital factor for better quality of life."

a_3 : "Urbanization fosters inequality as rural migrants often struggle to integrate into city life. Additionally, factors such as overcrowding contribute to worsening city living conditions."

a_2 : "Urbanization is essential for economic growth, which is crucial for the overall development of civilization."

a_1 : "Deforestation to expand cities worsens climate change and depletes ecosystems. One of the major drivers of deforestation is urbanization."

Now we can construct an argumentation framework from this debate where $\mathbf{Arg} = (a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4)$ and $\mathbf{attacks} = \{(a_1, a_2), (a_2, a_3), (a_3, a_4), (a_4, a_3)\}$. It may seem that only argument a_3 is capable to attack argument a_4 at a glance. But when inspected closely, it is obvious that both the arguments are about quality of life and they are attacking each other. The resulting digraph of this argumentation framework will look like figure 3.

The conflict free sets are: $\{a_1\}, \{a_2\}, \{a_3\}, \{a_4\}, \{a_1, a_3\}, \{a_1, a_4\}, \{a_2, a_4\}$, and \emptyset . The admissible sets are: $\{a_1\}, \{a_4\}, \{a_1, a_3\}, \{a_1, a_4\}$, and \emptyset . Among the seven non-empty conflict-free sets of arguments only $\{a_1, a_3\}, \{a_1, a_4\}$ and $\{a_2, a_4\}$ are maximal i.e. *naive* extension. The sets $\{a_1\}, \{a_1, a_3\}$ and $\{a_1, a_4\}$ belong to *complete* extension. The minimal complete extension is the *grounded* extension. Thus, the set is $\{a_1\}$. *Preferred* extension can also be easily deduced. As it is the subset maximal admissible set, the preferred extension has two sets: $\{a_1, a_3\}$ and $\{a_1, a_4\}$. As a_1 attacks a_2 and a_3 and a_4 attacks each other, following the definition of *stable* extension, we can observe that there are two stable extensions: $\{a_1, a_3\}$ and $\{a_1, a_4\}$. The definition of *semi-stable* extension dictates that if stable extension exists then semi-stable extension coincides with stable extension. So we already have found out the semi-stable extension for this example. The *ideal* extension here is $\{a_1\}$. This can also be simply found out using [8, Theorem 2.1] where Dung and Tony had shown that if the intersection of all preferred sets of arguments is admissible, then it coincides with the maximal ideal set. The greatest admissible set which is a subset of each semi-stable extension is also the set: $\{a_1\}$ which is the *eager* extension of this framework. The *stage* extension can be determined using the fact that it corresponds to the stable extension if the latter exists [12, Theorem 3.56].

Fig. 4. An argumentation framework where stable set does not exist

Example 5 (Argumentation framework - without stable set). The conflict free sets in figure 4 are $\{a_1\}$, $\{a_2\}$, $\{a_3\}$, and \emptyset . The only admissible set is \emptyset as no argument is able to defend itself from attack as it is a cyclical attack. As a result - complete, grounded, preferred, semi-stable, ideal and eager extension is also \emptyset . In this example no sets of arguments follow the requirement of conflict-freeness and ability to attack rest of the argument. Consequently, *no stable extension exists* here. Following the definition of stage extension we find that the range maximal conflict-free sets are: $\{a_1\}$, $\{a_2\}$, and $\{a_3\}$ [2].

In light of the above discussion, the following should be noted -

- The grounded extension is unique and the least complete extension.
- Each stable extension is also a preferred extension.
- Each preferred extension is also a complete extension but not vice versa.
- Stable extension does not always exist.
- While grounded extension coincides with the intersection of all complete extensions, the same is not applicable for preferred extensions. Baroni et al. [12] have shown this using an example.
- It may seem from the given two examples that stable semantics coincides with preferred semantics but that does not hold true in general.
- Every abstract argumentation framework admits a unique maximal ideal set of arguments [8].

3.2 Stability and Solution concepts

We previously noted that superadditivity motivates rational agents to form a grand coalition as the coalition maximizes the profit. However, we did not address whether this coalition would be stable. For example, if in example 3, S_2 and B goes into alliance for a selling price of 12 euro, then grand coalition will not form. In the coalition $C_6 = \{S_2, B\}$, both of them profits more than grand coalition outcome (C_7, \mathbf{x}_1) .

This brings us to the problem relating to stability of a coalition and solution concept of a game.

In a transferable utility game, the total gain can be divided in any manner among players. It is plausible that some players in a coalition receive a larger share while others receive a smaller share, depending, for example, on their contributions to the coalition's success. This leads to the following properties of payoff vector \mathbf{x} . We say $\mathbf{x} = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$ is,

- **feasible** iff $\sum_{n \in P} x_n \leq v(P)$,
- **efficient** iff $\sum_{n \in P} x_n = v(P)$ and
- **individually rational** iff $(\forall n \in P)v(\{n\}) \leq x_n$.

We call a payoff vector a an *imputation* iff a is efficient and individually rational. Intuitively, imputations allocate the entire amount of money to all players without any waste, ensuring that each agent receives at least as much as they would if they worked independently. We collect all such payoff vectors, which are called the imputations for G in set $IMP(G)$.

Example 6. It is clear that payoff vector \mathbf{x}_1 from example 3 is both *efficient* and *individually rational* making \mathbf{x}_1 an imputation, while \mathbf{x}_2 is *feasible*.

The stability of a coalition depends entirely on the share each member receives; if any member can gain more by joining another coalition, they will leave, effectively creating a new imputation. This is modelled by the notion of *domination* between imputations.

The first solution to a n-person cooperative game was proposed by von Neumann and Morgenstern [11]. Imputation $\mathbf{x} = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$ dominates imputation $\mathbf{y} = (y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n)$ via non-empty coalition C , denoted as $\mathbf{x} \xrightarrow{C} \mathbf{y}$, iff

- $(\forall k \in C)x_k > y_k$ and
- $\sum_{k \in C} x_k \leq v(C)$.

This states that rational agents will defect from imputation \mathbf{y} because (1)each of them will do *strictly* better in imputation \mathbf{x} . (2)The condition $\sum_{k \in C} x_k \leq v(C)$ says that players in coalition C can earn a profit that is at least as large as the payoff they receive according to x on their own. This situation motivates the players in coalition C to leave the grand coalition.

Example 7. Let us consider third imputation $\mathbf{x}_3 = (5, 4, 8)$ and \mathbf{x}_1 from example 3 for coalition C_7 . Clearly, $\mathbf{x}_3 = (5, 4, 8) \xrightarrow{S_2, B} \mathbf{x}_1 = (7, 3, 7)$.

The concept of domination is fundamental to the solution proposed by von Neumann and Morgenstern which we shall now define.

Definition 9 (Stable Set). A *stable set* of $G = (P, v)$ is a subset $I \subseteq IMP$ which satisfies following conditions.

1. *Internal stability:* No vector $\mathbf{x} \in I$ is dominated by another vector $\mathbf{y} \in I$.

2. *External stability*: $\forall \mathbf{y} \in IMP \setminus I$, there is a vector $\mathbf{x} \in I$ such that $\mathbf{x} \rightarrow \mathbf{y}$.

In this solution, internal stability guarantees that no payoff vector gets removed from I while external stability ensures that no other payoff vector is added further in I . This was described as “acceptable behaviors” in a society by von Neumann and Morgenstern. No behavior within this list is strictly superior to another behavior in the list, but for each unacceptable behavior there is an acceptable behavior that is preferable.

Although Von Neumann and Morgenstern proposed that every cooperative game with n participants is guaranteed to have at least one stable set, Lukas [9] proved that games without stable sets exist.

Our next solution concept is called *core*.

Definition 10 (Core). *The core of a cooperative game G is the set of all imputations \mathbf{x} defined as,*

$$\text{Core}(\mathbf{G}) = \{(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n) \in IMP(G) \mid \sum_{i \in C} a_i \geq v(C) \text{ for all coalitions } C \subseteq P\}.$$

If a set of players defects from the grand coalition where payoff has been distributed satisfying the condition in a *core* of a game, its not possible that every member of the deviating set profits from deviation. This ensures the stability.

How exactly are stable set and core related? It is easy to see that the core satisfies the condition of *internal stability* of stable sets. But it may not always ensure *external stability*. As a result, the core is contained in all stable sets when stable sets exist [16, section 2.3]. If it happens that the core and stable set coincide, then the stable set exists uniquely. This scenario is found in a class of games named *Convex Game* [15, section 3.1.2.5].

The next solution concept was defined by Roth in [14]. In his paper, Roth considered abstract games emerging from cooperative game $G = (X, >)$ where X is an arbitrary set whose members are called *outcomes* of the game and $> \subseteq X^2$ is an arbitrary binary relation defined on X and called *domination*. In a domination relation, an arbitrary point $x \in X$ dominates a set of points. Set of all such points is called the *dominion* of point x . Following this, *dominion* of a set of outcomes, $S \in X$, is defined as $D(S) = \{y \in X \mid (\exists x \in S) x > y \text{ for all } y \in X\}$. *Complement of $D(S)$* is defined as the set of outcomes undominated by any outcome in the set S and denoted as $U = X - S$. Roth then defined *subsolution* of such an abstract game as following.

Definition 11 (Subsolution). A subsolution of an abstract game $(X, >)$ is a set $S \subseteq X$ such that:

- $S \subseteq U(S)$ and
- $S = U^2(S) = U(U(S))$.

Evidently, condition (1) states that S is internally stable. Condition(2) requires more explanation but to express in a succinst manner - it simply says that S is self protecting once $S \subset U^2(S)$ gets satisfied. $S \supset U^2(S)$ implies S does not protect any point outside of S . Together, $S = U^2(S)$ implies S "overrules" everything except S , leaving only S as "sound".

Subsolution is a generalized form of the von Neumann-Morgenstern solution using abstract games.

Some important observations by Roth for the above mentioned solution concepts are,

1. Every solution is also a subsolution, since $S = U(S)$ implies $S = U^2(S)$.
2. The core is contained in every subsolution S , since points outside of S are dominated either by S or by $U(S) - S$.
3. A nonempty subsolution always exists in an abstract game [14, Theorem 1].
4. Intersection of all subsolutions is called **supercore** and **supercore** is also a subsolution [14, Theorem 2]. The supercore is empty set iff the core is empty.

Example 8 (Continuation of 3). In our example, we had $v(S_1) = v(S_2) = v(S_1, S_2) = v(B) = 0$ and $v(S_1, B) = v(S_2, B) = v(S_1, S_2, B) = 17$. A payoff vector (x_1, x_2, x_3) is an imputation iff it has (1) individual rationality and (2)efficiency. Thus, the vector has to follow the equations, $x_1 \geq 0, x_2 \geq 0, x_3 \geq 0, x_1 + x_2 + x_3 = v(P) = 17$. In order to be in the core, this imputation has to further satisfy, $x_1 + x_3 \geq 17, x_2 + x_3 \geq 17$, and $x_1 + x_2 \geq 0$. Note that $x_1 + x_3 \geq 17$ and $x_2 + x_3 \geq 17$ together imply that $x_1 + x_2 + 2x_3 \geq 34$. We are already given in the game, $x_1 + x_2 + x_3 = 17$. As a result, we shall have $x_1 \geq 0, x_2 \geq 0$ and $x_3 \geq 17$. Hence, the only imputation that can be in the core is $\mathbf{x} = (0, 0, 17)$. Roth showed the core in this example itself is a subsolution and therefore equal to supercore as well.

The game described above can be considered in a different setup. For example, a shoemaker has 2 left shoes and 1 right shoe. To make profit, the shoemaker will need to create a pair. The players in this case will be $P = (L_1, L_2, R)$, gain for non-empty coalitions will be $v(L_1) = v(L_2) = v(L_1, L_2) = v(R) = 0$ and $v(L_1, R) = v(L_2, R) = v(L_1, L_2, R) = 1$. The calculation will be same as before.

Having explored the details of solution concepts in cooperative game theory, how they relate to core and argumentation semantics, we can now examine how a solution concept aligns with the semantics.

3.3 Translating solution concepts

In this section, we will explore how the previously discussed solution concepts can be expressed within the framework of AF semantics. Furthermore, we will examine the existence and uniqueness of these concepts in relation to the established properties of existence and uniqueness in abstract AF semantics, whenever applicable.

While defining the first solution of cooperative game theory, von Neumann and Morgenstern abstracted away special structure associated with characteristic function games. Following them, Dung interpreted (IMP, \rightarrow) [14] as an abstract game. Dung has shown that every imputation serves as an argument to form a coalition. The domination relation between two imputations is an incentive for the dominated imputation to defect from grand coalition and this acts as an attack to the grand coalition. This translates the abstract game (IMP, \rightarrow) into an argumentation framework. Dung then demonstrated that different methods for resolving conflicts in the newly formed argumentation framework, $G = (IMP, \rightarrow)$, correspond to meaningful solution concepts in G . We will now present these correspondences, as defined by Dung and expanded upon by Young et al., in the following theorems. An overview can be in the figure 5.

3.3.1 Stable Set and Stable Extension If we go back to the definition of set of stable semantics of an abstract AF in section 3.1, definition 8, we shall see that it requires two properties - (1)conflict-freeness and (2)ability to attack the arguments outside of the stable set. It is easy to see that this is what has been described as internal stability and external stability. For internal stability no imputation dominates another one within I implying all the imputations are conflict-free. For external stability, every imputation not belonging to I is dominated by an imputation from I corresponding to the "ability to attack the arguments outside of the stable set".

Theorem 1. *Let G be a game and (IMP, \rightarrow) be its abstract game. If we view (IMP, \rightarrow) as an AF, then each of its stable extensions is a stable set of G , and vice versa. ([7, Theorem 37], [16, Theorem 1])*

The above theorem is based on NM-solution of a n-person cooperative game. We have already mentioned stable set of a game *does not always exist*. To show that

stable sets does not always exist in practically relevant argumentation system, we need only one such example. Dung used the example of "Stable Marriage Problem with Gays" as a practical scenario. We have also seen the argumentation framework in figure 4 depicts an abstract AF where stable semantics *does not exist*.

3.3.2 Core and Unattacked Arguments The second solution concept that we had mentioned in section 3.2 was the core. Earlier, we mentioned that - each attack indicates the potential for a group of agents to defect from the grand coalition in the AF (IMP, \rightarrow) . Based on this statement and the definition of the core, it follows that the core is essentially the set of unattacked arguments, as no agent has an incentive to defect from the core.

Theorem 2. *Let G be a game and (IMP, \rightarrow) be its abstract game. If we view (IMP, \rightarrow) as an AF, then its set of unattacked arguments corresponds exactly to the core. ([7, Theorem 38], [16, Theorem 2])*

3.3.3 Subsolution and Complete Extension It has been established that preferred extensions correspond to a specific solution concept in cooperative game theory. Additionally, it was previously noted that every preferred extension is also a complete extension. This leads to the question of whether any solution concept aligns with the complete semantics. We can find out the answer in the next theorem.

Theorem 3. *Let $G = (P, v)$ be a game and (IMP, \rightarrow) be its abstract game. When seen as an argumentation framework, the complete extensions (IMP, \rightarrow) are precisely the subsolutions [16, Theorem 3].*

Fig. 5. Translation from game theory to argumentation framework

In his paper, Roth has proven that every abstract game and thus every cooperative game has a subsolution. This guaranteed *existence* has also been shown by Ringo Baumann in [2] for complete semantics in an Argumentation framework (Theorem 2.16) also.

It has also been established in section 3.1 that stable extensions are also a type of complete extension. The cooperative game counterpart result of this has been demonstrated by Roth. He has shown that stable sets are a subset of subsolutions, indicating that subsolutions generalize stable sets.

In Definition 11, we had mentioned that "the core is contained in every subsolution" which is evident when we go back to Definition 8 where we had mentioned that every defended argument is contained in the set of complete semantics.

3.3.4 Supercore and Grounded Extension In Definition 8, we have said that a grounded extension "is the minimal complete extension". We just observed the translation between subsolution and complete extension. By incorporating Roth's result that the supercore of an abstract game is the intersection of all its subsolutions, we arrive at the following theorem. Consequently, the translation for grounded extension gets established.

Theorem 4. *The supercore of an abstract game is its grounded extension when viewed as an argumentation framework [16, Theorem 5].*

Ringo Baumann has shown that there are only two semantics which are *uniquely* defined [2]. They are *grounded* semantics and *ideal* semantics. Roth demonstrated that although subsolutions are generally not unique for abstract games but supercore provides one "natural" method for selecting a unique subsolution. Thus we can conclude that the supercore *uniquely exists* for all abstract games, and hence cooperative games. In Section 3.1, we noted that "each preferred extension is also a complete extension". The equivalent statement in cooperative game theory has been proven by Roth. In his paper, he has established that the supercore is a subsolution [14, Theorem 2].

3.3.5 \subseteq maximal Subsolution and Preferred Extension Since existence of stable semantics is not guaranteed in an AF, Dung proposed preferred solutions of n-person games by defining them as the preferred extensions of the corresponding argumentation system (IMP, \rightarrow). He also proved that preferred extension is guaranteed to be present in an AF [7, Theorem 11]. However the exact corresponding

counterpart in cooperative game theory was later established by Young et al. As we have already seen subsolutions of a game translate into complete extension, it is not difficult to see now that \subseteq maximal subsolution of an abstract game can be interpreted as preferred extension.

Theorem 5. *The \subseteq maximal Subsolution of an abstract game is its preferred extension when viewed as an argumentation framework.*

3.4 Summary

The correspondences between Dung’s argumentation semantics and the solution concepts of cooperative game can be found table 2. It also contains further results proven by Young et al.

Table 2. Summary of solution concept and abstract AF and their correspondence

Abstract AF	Cooperative Game
Set of arguments Arg	Set of imputations IMP
Attack relation $attacks$	Domination relation \rightarrow
Argumentation Framework ($Arg, attacks$)	Abstract Game (IMP, \rightarrow)
Unattacked arguments	The Core
Stable Semantics	Stable Sets
Complete Semantics	Subsolutions
The Grounded Semantics	The Supercore
Preferred Semantics	\subseteq maximal Subsolutions

We have also discussed the relation of core with other solution concepts in section 3.2. Concept of existence and uniqueness has been discussed in as part of formalization of acceptability semantics as well as establishing the transition between cooperative game theory and abstract AF. We have observed ideal semantics is closely related to preferred extension as it is a subset of each preferred and grounded extension as maximal ideal set of arguments is a superset of the grounded set and is also a subset of the intersection of all preferred sets. This has been shown by Dung in [8]. They further proved that maximal ideal set of arguments is also complete one. These findings can be helpful in future to find a translation from a solution concept of cooperative game theory to ideal semantics of abstract AF.

4 Conclusion

Much work has been done to investigate the relationship between argumentation and game theory more generally. For example, in [5] Cheng et al. used their framework to

solve normal-form games, providing explanation for solution concepts. Rahwan and Larson have used argumentation theory to analyse non-cooperative games in [13]. Matt and Toni defined a two players repeated game of argumentation strategy where the proponent’s long run expected payoff (the game’s value) was defined as a value of strength for the argument he embraces [10]. Baroni et al. also applied minimax theorem to measure argument strength in [1].

In this report, we have discussed various solution concepts of cooperative game theory and how they have a counterpart on abstract argumentation framework. There is scope of future work regarding other semantics such as non Dung semantics like ideal, eager, stage etc and other solution concepts such as Shapley value which is concerned with measuring the payoff to each agent given their marginal contribution in each coalition, averaged over all coalitions.

References

1. Baroni, P., Comini, G., Rago, A., Toni, F.: Abstract games of argumentation strategy and game-theoretical argument strength. In: An, B., Bazzan, A.L.C., Leite, J., Villata, S., van der Torre, L.W.N. (eds.) PRIMA 2017: Principles and Practice of Multi-Agent Systems - 20th International Conference, Nice, France, October 30 - November 3, 2017, Proceedings. Lecture Notes in Computer Science, vol. 10621, pp. 403–419. Springer (2017). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-69131-2_24, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-69131-2_24
2. Baumann, R.: On the nature of argumentation semantics: Existence and uniqueness, expressibility, and replaceability. FLAP 4(8) (2017), <http://www.collegepublications.co.uk/downloads/ifcolog00017.pdf>
3. Bench-Capon, T.J.M., Dunne, P.E.: Argumentation in artificial intelligence. Artif. Intell. 171(10-15), 619–641 (2007). <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ARTINT.2007.05.001>, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.artint.2007.05.001>
4. Caminada, M.: Comparing two unique extension semantics for formal argumentation: Ideal and eager. Proc. of the 19th Belgian-Dutch Conference on Artificial Intelligence (01 2007)
5. Cheng, Y., Liao, B., Luo, J.: Applying abstract argumentation to normal-form games. In: Calvaresi, D., Najjar, A., Winikoff, M., Främling, K. (eds.) Explainable and Transparent AI and Multi-Agent Systems - Third International Workshop, EXTRAAMAS 2021, Virtual Event, May 3-7, 2021, Revised Selected Papers. Lecture Notes in Computer Science, vol. 12688, pp. 314–328. Springer (2021). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-82017-6_19, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-82017-6_19
6. Davis, M.D.: Chapter 4 utility theory. In: Game Theory: A Nontechnical Introduction (1997)
7. Dung, P.M.: On the acceptability of arguments and its fundamental role in nonmonotonic reasoning, logic programming and n-person games. Artif. Intell. 77(2), 321–358 (1995). [https://doi.org/10.1016/0004-3702\(94\)00041-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/0004-3702(94)00041-X), [https://doi.org/10.1016/0004-3702\(94\)00041-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/0004-3702(94)00041-X)
8. Dung, P.M., Mancarella, P., Toni, F.: Computing ideal sceptical argumentation. Artif. Intell. 171(10-15), 642–674 (2007). <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ARTINT.2007.05.003>, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.artint.2007.05.003>
9. Lucas, W.F.: The Proof That a Game May Not Have a Solution. RAND Corporation, Santa Monica, CA (1968)
10. Matt, P., Toni, F.: A game-theoretic measure of argument strength for abstract argumentation. In: Hölldobler, S., Lutz, C., Wansing, H. (eds.) Logics in Artificial Intelligence, 11th European Conference, JELIA 2008, Dresden, Germany, September 28 - October 1, 2008. Proceedings. Lecture

- Notes in Computer Science, vol. 5293, pp. 285–297. Springer (2008). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-540-87803-2_24, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-540-87803-2_24
11. von Neumann, J., Morgenstern, O.: Theory of Games and Economic Behavior (60th-Anniversary Edition). Princeton University Press (2007), <http://press.princeton.edu/titles/7802.html>
 12. Pietro Baroni, Martin Caminada, M.G.: Chapter 4 abstract argumentation frameworks and their semantics. In: Handbook of Formal Argumentation (2018)
 13. Rahwan, I., Larson, K.: Argumentation and game theory. In: Simari, G.R., Rahwan, I. (eds.) Argumentation in Artificial Intelligence, pp. 321–339. Springer (2009). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-0-387-98197-0_16, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-0-387-98197-0_16
 14. Roth, A.E.: Subsolutions and the supercore of cooperative games. Math. Oper. Res. **1**(1), 43–49 (1976). <https://doi.org/10.1287/MOOR.1.1.43>, <https://doi.org/10.1287/moor.1.1.43>
 15. Rothe, J. (ed.): Economics and Computation, An Introduction to Algorithmic Game Theory, Computational Social Choice, and Fair Division. Springer texts in business and economics, Springer (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-662-47904-9>, <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-662-47904-9>
 16. Young, A.P., Marzagão, D.K., Murphy, J.: Applying abstract argumentation theory to cooperative game theory. In: Santini, F., Toniolo, A. (eds.) Proceedings of the 3rd Workshop on Advances In Argumentation In Artificial Intelligence co-located with the 18th International Conference of the Italian Association for Artificial Intelligence (AI*IA 2019), Rende, Italy, November 19-22, 2019. CEUR Workshop Proceedings, vol. 2528, pp. 105–119. CEUR-WS.org (2019), https://ceur-ws.org/Vol-2528/10_Young_et_al_AI3_2019.pdf